

INTERLAMINAR TOUGHENING OF RESIN TRANSFER MOULDED GLASS FIBRE EPOXY LAMINATES BY POLYCAPROLACTONE ELECTROSPUN NANOFIBRES

Sam van der Heijden¹, Lode Daelemans¹, Ives De Baere², Hubert Rahier³, Wim Van Paepegem²,
Karen De Clerck¹

¹ Ghent University, Department of Textiles, Technologiepark-Zwijnaarde 907, B-9052 Zwijnaarde,
Belgium Email: Karen.DeClerck@ugent.be

² Ghent University, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Technologiepark-Zwijnaarde
903, B-9052 Zwijnaarde, Belgium

³ Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Department Materials and Chemistry, Pleinlaan 2, B-1050 Brussels,
Belgium

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ABSTRACT

Delamination and brittle matrix fracture has since long been a problem of fibre reinforced composites. This paper investigates if polycaprolactone (PCL) nanofibre nonwovens can increase the interlaminar fracture toughness of resin transfer moulded glass fibre/epoxy laminates, without causing problems during impregnation and without negatively affecting other (mechanical) properties.

The mode I fracture toughness was shown to be dependent on both the nanofibre content as well as on how the nanofibres were introduced into the laminates. Almost 100% improvement in fracture toughness could be achieved by electrospinning the PCL nanofibres on both sides of the glass fibre mats prior to impregnation. This led to a mode I fracture toughness of over 1200 J/m². It could be concluded that even state of the art infusion resins with a high intrinsic fracture toughness can benefit significantly from nanofibre toughening.

1 INTRODUCTION

Delamination and brittle matrix fracture has since long been a problem of fibre reinforced composites [1-3]. A lot of research has been devoted to prevent delamination by modifying the epoxy matrix, either by chemically modifying the resin and hardener components, e.g. by using dendritic hyper branched polymers [4], or by adding additional components to the epoxy resin, e.g. mixing in rubber particles or creating specific thermoplastic phase morphologies in the matrix [5-12]. Although creating a rubbery phase inside of the epoxy matrix often increases the fracture toughness of the laminates, this increase is often accompanied with a decrease in other mechanical properties such as stiffness and strength. In the research of M.R. Dadfar et al. the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic}) of the glass epoxy laminates increased from 220 J/m² to about 500 J/m² whereas the elastic modulus and tensile strength went down from 28.4 GPa to 17.8 GPa and 584 MPa to 489 MPa respectively [12]. More recently, the effect of nanoparticles such as nanoclay, carbon nanotubes, nanowhiskers and vapour grown carbon nanofibres on the toughness of the epoxy matrix has been studied [13-15]. Although an increase in bulk fracture toughness could often be accomplished by adding these additional components to the epoxy matrix, the absolute increase in interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite laminates remains moderate at best [16-18]. For example, Masahiro Arai et al. could improve the mode I initiation interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic,ini}) of carbon fibre epoxy laminates from 200 J/m² to approximately 300 J/m² whereas the propagation fracture toughness (G_{Ic,prop}) increased from 500 J/m² to 650 J/m². W.X. Wang et al. obtained an increase in G_{Ic} from 140 J/m² to 220 J/m² using nanowhiskers [17, 18]. In addition, all the toughening systems mentioned above have two common disadvantages: (1) it is difficult to get a homogeneous dispersion

of extra phases into the epoxy matrix and final laminate, and (2) the resin viscosity increases tremendously when these phases are mixed into the resin prior to moulding. These problems are of course very problematic for all infusion applications, such as resin transfer moulding (RTM).

Thermoplastic nanofibrous structures could offer a solution for the increased viscosity and the inhomogeneous dispersion, as nanofibre nonwovens can be readily deposited in between the primary reinforcing fibre layers prior to infusion. Thus, the viscosity of the epoxy resin is not affected. Although the idea of using electrospun nanofibres as a secondary reinforcement in composite structures has already been proposed by Dzenis and Reneker in 1999 [19], it is only since the last few years that the interlaminar toughening effects of thermoplastic nanofibres are being reported. Bilge et al. showed that P(St-co-GMA) nanofibrous interlayers can improve the open hole strength of carbon/epoxy laminates [20]. Palazetti et al. reported about the use of nylon 6.6 nanofibrous mats to increase the interlaminar properties and impact resistance of composites. The GIC increased from 473 J/m² to 496 J/m² [21, 22]. Jin Zhang et al. showed that GIC of a carbon fibre epoxy laminate could be increased from 175 J/m² to about 320 J/m² (depending on nanofibre diameter and interlayer thickness) using polyetherketone cardo nanofibres [23]. Gang Li et al. used polysulfone (PSF) nanofibres to increase the GIC of carbon fibre epoxy laminates from 310 J/m² up to 870 J/m². Furthermore, it was shown that the use of PSF nanofibrous nonwovens leads to a more efficient toughening than the use of PSF films of equal weight [24].

All research papers mentioned above used prepreg material on which the nanofibres were deposited. Although prepreg materials are often used in industry, e.g. aerospace industry almost exclusively uses prepreg materials, resin infusion has substantially gained importance for the production of big composite parts such as windmill blades and yacht parts. Modern infusion moulded laminates make use of low viscosity and high toughness epoxy resins. The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of these laminates is typically higher than 600 J/m². This fracture toughness is much higher than that of the prepreg materials studied so far in literature [20-24]. This paper aims to investigate if high toughness polycaprolactone (PCL) nanofibre nonwovens can increase the interlaminar fracture toughness of these infusion moulded laminates even more, without causing problems during infusion.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODES

2.1 Materials

All composite laminates were reinforced with unidirectional E-glass fabric (Roviglas R17/475). The reinforcement had a weight of 475 g/m² in the fibre direction and a weight of 17 g/m² in the perpendicular direction.

The epoxy resin was composed of EPIKOTE resin MGS RIMR 135 with EPIKURE curing agent MGS RIMH 137 (Momentive). This is an infusion resin designed for windmill applications and it has a low viscosity and a high toughness.

Polycaprolactone pellets and solvents 98 v% formic acid and 99.8 v% acetic acid were supplied by Sigma–Aldrich and used as received.

2.2 Electrospinning

Prior to electrospinning, an appropriate solvent system was selected to allow for the production of nanofibre nonwovens in a stable and reproducible way. Furthermore the toxicity of the solvent system should be low, in order to make the system relevant for industrial application.

PCL can be electrospun in a stable and reproducible manner from a 1:1 formic acid/acetic acid solution which has a relatively low toxicity [25, 26]. Therefore, 14 wt% of PCL was dissolved in a 1:1 solution of formic acid and acetic acid. To obtain large uniform nanofibrous nonwovens, the nanofibres were produced using a multi-nozzle electrospinning set-up. This multi-nozzle method, an in house developed technology [22], diverges from a mono-nozzle set-up mainly by the number of nozzles, the general methodology itself is identical. It consists out of 32 nozzles, each fed by 16 syringes. The nozzles are placed in 4 alternating rows which have a movement in the transverse direction to ensure uniform deposition of nanofibres. In the meantime, a grounded collector is moving in the longitudinal or production direction. The speed of the groundcollector is adjusted to

obtain the required areal density of the nanofibrous nonwovens. All nanofibrous nonwovens were spun in a conditioned room at 23 ± 2 °C and 50 ± 5 % RH. The tip-to-collector distance was 12.5 cm and the flow rate was set at 1 ml/h (per nozzle). The voltage was set between 20 kV and 25 kV until a stable process was achieved. Nanofibrous structures were both produced as stand-alone structures as well as deposited structures. The stand-alone nanofibrous nonwovens were electrospun on an aluminium foil, and were peeled off afterwards. The deposited structures were directly electrospun onto glass fibre mats. In both cases the fibre diameter of the nanofibrous structures was 400 ± 100 nm.

2.3 Vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding and preparation of PCL toughened laminates

The composite laminates were manufactured by vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM). The glass fibre mats were stacked into a steel mould, either in a $[0^\circ]_8$ or in a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_2$ configuration. All laminates consisted out of 8 layers of glass fibres and had a total thickness of 3 ± 0.1 mm. Three different configurations were used to introduce the nanofibres into the laminates. In addition to these three configurations, reference samples were produced containing only glass fibres.

In the first configuration a single layer of nanofibres was directly electrospun on one side of the glass fibre mats. These mats are stacked on top of each other. Hence, the interlayer of two neighbouring plies contains a single layer of nanofibre nonwoven. This configuration will be referred to as the single layer deposited configuration (SLD).

The second configuration, referred to as the double layer deposited configuration (DLD), consists out of one layer of nanofibres electrospun on each side of the glass fibre mats. Therefore, the interlayer of two neighbouring plies contained two layers of nanofibres on top of each other.

The third configuration was named the interlayered configuration (IL). This configuration consists of standalone nanofibre nonwovens placed in between the glass fibre mats. Therefore, the interlayer contains one layer of nanofibrous nonwoven, but that layer is not directly electrospun onto the glass fibre mats.

The samples prepared for the tensile tests contained nanofibrous nonwoven, according to the above configurations, in each interlayer. For the double cantilever beam samples (DCB), the nanofibrous nonwoven was incorporated in the tested interlayer.

Prior to infusion, the resin and hardener were mixed in a 100:30 mass ratio. A mechanical stirrer was used to ensure good mixing of resin and hardener. After mixing, the epoxy resin was placed under vacuum for 15 min to remove any air introduced during mixing.

After injection, the glass-epoxy laminate is first cured at room temperature for 24 hours and then post-cured for 15 hours at 80 °C. It should be noted that although the temperature in the post curing step is above the melting region of PCL (approximately at 60 °C) the curing at room temperature is well below the melting region[27].

2.4 Characterisation

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Joel Quanta 200 F FE-SEM) was used to investigate the fibre diameter of the electrospun nanofibres as well as the delamination fracture surface of the laminates. Prior to the SEM-measurements, the specimens were coated by a gold sputter coater (Balzers Union SCD 030). An optical microscope, an Olympus BX51 with an Olympus UC30 camera, was used to visualise delamination cracks in the cross section of the composite laminates as well as to determine the thickness of the interlayer between two neighbouring plies.

Mode I delamination fracture toughness was measured by DCB experiments on an electromechanical Instron 5800R machine following the ASTM D 5528 (2013) standard. Five samples were tested for each configuration. All DCB experiments were performed on unidirectional laminates and piano hinges were used to transfer the load to the sample. The dimensions of the DCB samples were 20 x 160 x 3 mm and the initial delamination length was 50 mm and was created using a release film with a thickness of 30µm. The crack propagation in the DCB samples was followed using a traveling microscope. Throughout this paper, different cross sections of these DCB samples will be shown, a coordinate system is used to indicate the glass fibre direction (X), the direction perpendicular to the unidirectional glass fibres (Y) and the

thickness direction (Z).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The effect of nanofibre nonwoven placement on the interlaminar fracture toughness

Three different configurations (single layer deposited (SLD), double layer deposited (DLD) and interlayered (IL) were tested in comparison to the reference configuration without nanofibres.

Figure 1.A shows the mode I fracture toughness for the three different nanofibre stacking configurations as a function of the crack length. These values were calculated according to ASTM D 5528 from the load displacement curve (Figure 1.B) and the measured crack length recorded by a traveling microscope. The nanofibre content in the interlayer was 5 g/m^2 for each configuration implying that the DLD samples had 2.5 g/m^2 of nanofibres in each deposited nanofibre layer. It can be noted that both the IL configuration as well as the SLD configuration only show a marginal improvement over the reference laminates. In contrast the DLD configuration showed a substantial improvement. Both the initiation fracture toughness ($G_{Ic,ini}$) and the propagation fracture toughness ($G_{Ic,prop}$) were increased by about 430 J/m^2 and 280 J/m^2 respectively compared to the reference laminate. Taking into account that due to the selection of a high toughness infusion resin, the reference material already had a $G_{Ic,ini}$ of $640 \pm 60 \text{ J/m}^2$, the mode I initiation fracture toughness of the DLD configuration was found to be as high as $1070 \pm 130 \text{ J/m}^2$.

Figure 1: Mode I fracture toughness as a function of crack length (A) and load-displacement curves (B), showing significant increases when a double layer deposited (DLD) configuration is used as compared to a single layer deposited configuration (SLD) or interlayered configuration (IL).

An explanation for the remarkable difference between these configurations is found by visually examining the fracture surface of the DCB samples. Figure 2 shows a comparison between a SLD configuration and a DLD configuration. For the SLD configuration, the PCL nanofiber layer can be found on the fractured sample half that contained the glass fibre mat on which the PCL nanofibres were deposited. Therefore, the delamination crack propagated between the embedded nanofibrous layer and the glass fibre mat directly above it. The microscopic analysis also supports this hypothesis, see Section 3.4. It is assumed that a better adhesion/interaction of the nanofibres with the glass fibres in case the nanofibres are directly deposited on top of the glass fibres during the electrospinning process is the reason for the crack propagating above the toughened nanofibre layer. As such, the delamination crack did not go through the toughened interlayer. Hence, only marginal improvement compared to the reference was found.

Figure 2: Fracture surface of DCB samples showing how the impregnated nanofibrous PCL nonwoven is distributed over the two sample halves after fracture in case of the DLD (left) and SLD (right) configuration.

In contrast, for the DLD configuration, parts of the embedded nanofibrous layer can be found on both halves of the fractured sample. This indicates that the delamination crack propagated, at least partially, through the toughened interlayer. Therefore, in the DLD configuration, more energy was required for the delamination crack to propagate through the nanofibre toughened interlayer, and hence, the fracture toughness of the DLD configuration is significantly higher than the SLD configuration.

In a DCB experiment, a release film is used to initiate the delamination in between the central plies of the laminate. Thus the film was on top of the nanofibrous nonwoven for the SLD configuration, whereas for the DLD configuration, the film was in between two nanofibrous layers. To verify the film placement had no effect on the observed differences between the SLD and DLD configurations, modified DCB specimens were designed in which there was a 1mm gap between the nanofibrous reinforcement and the release film. Thus the delamination crack started in front of the nanofibrous reinforcement. No difference in mode I fracture toughness was found for these modified specimens compared to the standard designed specimens. Again a substantial improvement for the DLD configuration was observed compared to the other configurations.

3.5 The effect of nanofibre content on the interlaminar fracture toughness

The nanofibre content is varied from 2.5 g/m² to 40 g/m² of PCL nanofibres in the interlayer. Figure 6 illustrates the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the resin transfer moulded laminates, both for the SLD and the DLD configuration.

For the SLD configuration the fracture toughness shows no important variation with nanofibre content and has a value of around 765 ± 100 J/m² for initiation and 1060 ± 100 J/m² for propagation. These values are slightly better than the 640 J/m² and 950 J/m² obtained for the reference laminates without nanofibres in the interlayer. It should also be noted that even though the thickness of the interlayer increases significantly when high amounts of PCL nanofibres are added to the laminate, the interlaminar fracture toughness remains almost constant. This observation supports the hypothesis that in case of a SLD configuration, the crack mainly propagates above the nanofibre layer. Hence, the obtained fracture toughness is less dependent on the nanofibre content.

For the DLD configuration, the initiation fracture toughness increases rapidly with increasing nanofibre content up to a value of 1070 ± 130 J/m² when 5 g/m² of nanofibres are added in the interlayer. When more than 5 g/m² of nanofibres are added to the interlayer, the initiation fracture toughness still increases although at a much slower rate. For the maximum value of 20 g/m² the initiation fracture toughness increased up to 1240 ± 170 J/m². This is an increase of almost 100%

compared to the reference laminates. As opposed to the initiation fracture toughness, the propagation fracture toughness is shown to be relatively independent of the nanofibre content. The propagation fracture toughness is approximately 1200 J/m^2 for all nanofibre contents. This is around 250 J/m^2 higher compared to the reference laminates. Overall it is clear the fracture toughness of the laminate increased significantly when a DLD configuration is used.

toughened interlayer when a DLD configuration is used.

Figure 6: Effect of PCL nanofibre content on $G_{IC,ini}$ and $G_{IC,prop}$ for single and double layer deposited configurations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of PCL nanofibres on the interlaminar fracture toughness of resin transfer moulded glass fibre epoxy laminates was studied. The infusion process is not negatively influenced by the presence of the PCL nanofibres. The way in which the nanofibres are arranged into the laminate has a major effect on the mode I fracture toughness of the laminates. A DLD configuration in which the nanofibres were directly electrospun on both sides of the unidirectional glass fibre mats is clearly superior over the other tested configurations. More specifically, the obtained improvement was a function of the nanofibre content in the DLD samples. For a nanofibre content of 20 g/m^2 in the interlayers, an improvement in initiation interlaminar fracture toughness of almost 100% was obtained. The initiation fracture toughness increased from 640 J/m^2 for the reference laminates to 1230 J/m^2 for the nanofibre toughened laminates.

It can be concluded that even state-of-the-art infusion resins can benefit from nanofibre toughening. This toughening effect was attributed to a good adhesion of deposited nanofibres onto the glass fibre mats, as well as to the inherent tough and ductile properties of the PCL nanofibres themselves. It is assumed that these properties resulted in glass fibre bridging as well as a crack path deflection effect during initiation of the delamination. Due to this crack path deflection, the delamination crack propagated partially through the nanofibre toughened interlayer (in case of a DLD configuration) resulting in a significant increase in fracture toughness.

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